

Technology for Developing Listening Skills Using Authentic Materials in the Process of Teaching a Foreign Language

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Abstract: The article considers about the technology of developing listening skills using authentic materials in the process of teaching a foreign language. It also analyzes the sources from which text material can be drawn for exercises in listening comprehension.

Keys words: speech perception, listening skills, use of authentic materials, understanding of words, bookish writing style, long sentences, idiomatic and figurative language.

Since the successful course of the speech perception process depends on the quality and tempo of speaking the perceived material in the form of inner speech, a good level of perception can only be achieved with material that has been sufficiently worked out in the process of speaking or reading. Therefore, texts designed for listening comprehension should be built mainly on worked out material. But we must not lose sight of the fact that understanding the content of the text is practically possible without understanding some words. In particular, understanding words denoting the degree of quality, such as *rather*, *very*, *too*.

Perception of a text containing unfamiliar words is partly similar to perception of a text in which some words are missing. In order to fill this gap, it is necessary to understand the speaker's intention well and to be interested in what you hear, only in this case the listener's thought works intensively and fruitfully. In order for the listener's thought to overtake the narrator, the perceived text must be absolutely accessible in content and language, which means that the text must be based on familiar and already sufficiently well-assimilated grammatical material so that the student can easily rely on it, and contain such a number of new words that there is no more than one for five or six sentences. Naturally, there cannot be more than one unfamiliar word in a sentence [2].

A number of compelling arguments can be given in favor of the fact that listening comprehension should be taught using the same material as speaking, and not using material intended for reading. Such features of the bookish written style as long sentences, idiomaticity and figurative language are extremely difficult for listening comprehension. The goal at school is not to teach listening comprehension of lectures and reports, it is only necessary to achieve students' understanding of colloquial speech on everyday topics. They should practice understanding such material.

An analysis of the conditions influencing listening comprehension serves as the basis for establishing what the content of the texts and the form of presentation should be.

It is advisable to start with disparate material, the perception of which is specifically aimed at developing the ability to overcome isolated linguistic difficulties. Then you should move on to using very short coherent texts (3-6 sentences), which would combine both linguistic difficulties and difficulties associated

with the perception of content.

Experience shows that it is advisable to start with the simplest and closest to students descriptive texts in content, thematically related to the text of the textbook covered. Then you can move on to descriptive texts related to the lives of students. The description of one's city, school, and the description of the students' appearance are perceived very well. Descriptive texts are always compositionally simple and devoid of any subtext.

When students gain some experience in perceiving texts by ear, they should move on to texts with a new topic and content for the students. The text volume increases to 10-12 sentences. Gradually, you can move on to narrative texts without an entertaining plot. Starting from the moment when a sufficient stock of language material has accumulated, providing the ability to understand narrative texts with an entertaining plot, such texts should take a large place in teaching speech perception by ear. They are interesting in content and therefore make students want to understand what they hear. According to the observations of Zolotnitskaya S.P., such texts can include a significantly greater number of difficulties than descriptive texts, and, nevertheless, students understand them better [1].

The last question concerns the sources from which text material can be drawn for listening comprehension exercises. At present, special books for teachers are not yet published that would contain strictly graded material selected for each class. Therefore, teachers have to select suitable texts themselves. The most successful, both in the form of presentation and in terms of interest to listeners, is a teacher's story about himself and his loved ones. This does not require any special entertainment. The most ordinary facts, small details related to the life of their teacher make him closer, more accessible to students and meet a grateful audience. However, no matter how well stories of this kind are received, they, naturally, cannot fill all the lessons devoted to teaching listening comprehension in all classes. It is necessary to have a constant supply of text material, and here again it is necessary to turn to literary sources. It is useful to use periodicals. In terms of form, first-person stories are best suited for this purpose. Any material borrowed from literature requires some processing - cutting out unnecessary details, excluding or replacing unfamiliar words, dividing long and complex phrases into simple and short ones. Literary material mainly provides a plot, and it must be presented in your own words. We advise each teacher to adapt these texts to the level of their students.

Short stories about things from their own perspective - about what they are made of, what they look like, how they serve a person - can serve as good material for listening - can be used as a model for composing whole series of various descriptions.

Texts intended for listening are best not read, but told by looking at the text. Some stories can be given to individual students so that they can familiarize themselves with them in advance and then tell them in class. We also recommend recording the texts on tape. Where there is direct speech, different speakers can be involved in the recording. This will simultaneously solve several problems - it will make the teacher's work easier in the lesson, give him the opportunity to use the finished text in the next school year, and will allow the student to practice listening to speech at different speeds and in different voices.

It can be concluded that the selection of material and the choice of the type of listening at all stages of training depends on the communicative situation in which listening comprehension occurs, taking into account the difficulties in listening to authentic materials, taking into account the age psychology of schoolchildren when choosing a topic. Thus, a well-thought-out organization of the educational process, clarity and logic of presentation, maximum reliance on active thinking, a variety of teaching methods, clarification of perception tasks allow you to create internal motivation, direct students' attention to moments that will help program future practical activities with the perceived material.

In conclusion, we will provide several sample texts for understanding speech by ear. They are arranged in order of increasing difficulty, but are not confined to any particular class, since the level of preparation of students in this area is not uniform among different teachers and in different schools, and therefore it is impossible to create texts equally suitable for everyone. This is due to the fact that currently, listening

comprehension training is not carried out systematically in all schools.

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